
PREVALENCE OF SUBSTANCE ABUSE AMONG TERTIARY INSTITUTION STUDENTS IN NIGERIA (STUDY OF NIGERIAN ARMY COLLEGE OF ENVIRONMENTAL SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY MAKURDI)

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ABSTRACT

Youth populations are vulnerable to substance use particularly in developing countries where circumstances may be favor for it. The research study therefore investigates on the prevalence of substance abuse among tertiary institution students in Nigeria. Descriptive survey design was used in the study in which data was collected using self-structured questionnaire. Simple random sampling was used to select 357 respondents where only 341 was retrieved and used. Social pressure, Peer pressure, Curiosity or experimentation, Rebellion against constituted authority among others are the factors identify for Substance consumption. From research question two it was discovered that level of consumption of substance abuse is high representing 281 (82 %). Out of many substances abuse by the 281 respondents is tobacco 8.9%, alcohol/beer 53%, tramadol 10.7%, cough syrup 16%, whiskey 5.7% and diazepam 1.8%. Alcohol/ Beer is the highly consumed substance. Majority of the respondents take substances every day 56.2% and every week 27.1%. Those between 21-30 years of age representing 175 (62.3%) are the majority who begins substance abuse. Most of the respondents 189 (67.3%) abuse substances without their parents /guardians been aware of the act. Panic, Irritability, Depression, Anxiety, Psychosis among others are the consequences of Substance. in conclusion, there is high prevalence of substance abuse among tertiary institution students in Nigeria. The creation of awareness and health education should be continued to fully combat the problem of abuse. Some of the strategies include strict enforcement of law against illicit substances abuse, school management and parent need to establish mechanism to reduce amount of money given to students, friends/peer groups control measures by parent/ guardians, punishment of substance abuses by control agencies such as National Drug Law Enforcement Agency and then pharmacies should be restricted against selling dangerous substances.

Key Words: Prevalence, Substance, Abuse, and Substance Abuse.

I. INTRODUCTION

Substance Abuse present a significant public health problem with far reaching ramifications ranging from poor health outcomes to diminished production in all sectors of the economy, insecurity and non-attainment of national development goals (NDLEA, 2017). Intoxicants alter the state of a person's mental, social and physical well-being thereby influencing his/her thoughts, realities, decisions and actions (NDLEA, 2017).

Previous studies such as that of Everest (2005) and NDLEA (2007) have revealed early engagement by Nigerian youth in Substance Abuse. Ndeti et al (2010), in an article published by Routledge in (2014) found that alcohol, tobacco, Khat and cannabis were the most reported substances of use by the youths in Nigeria, with user prevalence rates of 5.2%, 3.8%, 3.2% and 1.7% respectively. Many studies have established that abuse of substance among the youth is worrisome and alarming, but the pertinent question to be asked here is that are youths and substance abuser were aware of implication of these illicit drugs to their health, social, moral among other factors, it is against this background, the researcher sought to investigate from tertiary institution students in Nigeria with a focus on Nigerian Army College of Environmental Science and Technology Makurdi.

Globally, it is estimated that in 2012, some 243 million people (range: 162 million-324 million) corresponding to some 5.2 per cent (range: 3.5-7.0 per cent) of the world population aged 15-64 had used an illicit drug-mainly a substance belonging to the cannabis, opioid, cocaine or amphetamine-type stimulant (ATS) group-at least once in the previous year (United nations, 2014). Drug use continues to exact a significant toll, with valuable human lives and productive years of many persons being lost. An estimated 183,000 (range: 95,000-226,000) drug-related deaths were reported in 2012. That figure corresponds to a mortality rate of 40.0 (range: 20.8-49.3) deaths per million among the population aged 15-64 years.

There is a growing public concern in our country, Nigeria, about involvement of adolescents and young adult in Substance Abuse, which is defined as the non - medical use of substances by human beings that may modify one or more of its functions and may impair an individual ability to function effectively and may result in social physical or emotional harm (United nations, 2014). While it is universally accepted that drugs can be of tremendous benefit to man and society, it is also acknowledged that inappropriate use of drugs can be harmful to man. The personal, social and public health problems associated with psychoactive substance use, have continued to arouse worldwide interest and concern. Various reports and researches conducted have illustrated this phenomenon. Drugs/substance abuse is a worldwide hazard with dangerous complications that affect many countries around the globe, Nigeria inclusive. The problem varies from place to place.

In Africa, a study on secondary school students' knowledge of the dangers associated with alcohol, tobacco and marijuana done in Anambra State, Nigeria found that students were not aware of most of the dangers associated with alcohol, tobacco and marijuana (Nwankwo, Obi, & Nwosu, 2012). In Ilorin, Nigeria, an analysis of responses on the current and lifetime use of eleven substances of abuse, their frequency of use, and the effect of gender and school location on use trends was done. It revealed that although a significant increase in current use rates was recorded for alcohol, cannabis, mild stimulants and Hypnos datives, all of these substances (except stimulants) showed a shift towards less frequent use in 1993. The only consistent gender effect was found for smoking, which remained significantly a male activity (Adelekan, 2013).

In Nigeria, Substance Abuse is a serious public health issue to the extent that the Senate wanted Substance Abuse declared a national disaster (Daily nation, Saturday July 6th, 2013). The senators opined that classifying the problem that had wrecked the lives of many youths as a national disaster would make it easier for authorities to focus and deal with it. The National Drug Law Enforcement Agency (NDLEA) (2012) rapid situation assessment of drugs and substance abuse in Nigeria showed that 5.5% of Nigerians were dependent on alcohol; 4.5 % were dependent on tobacco; 1.5% were dependent on miraa while 0.4% were dependent on bhang use (NDLEA, 2012).

Many factors have been indicted as the causes of Substance Abuse, Haladu, (2013) gave the following as the main causes. Curiosity to experiment the unknown facts about drugs thus motivates adolescents into drug use. The first experience in Substance Abuse produces a state of arousal such as happiness and pleasure which in turn motivate them to continue. Peer pressure plays a major role in influencing many adolescents into Substance Abuse. This is because peer pressure is a fact of teenage and youth life. As they try to depend less on parents, they show more dependency on their friends. In Nigeria, as other parts of the world, one may not enjoy the company of others unless he conforms to their norms (NDLEA, 2012). Many parents have no time to supervise their sons and daughters. Some parents have little or no interaction with family members, while others put pressure on their children to pass exams or perform better in their studies. Adolescents with personality problems arising from social conditions have been found to abuse drugs. The social and economic status of most Nigerians is below average.

However, poverty is widespread, broken homes and unemployment is on the increase, therefore our youths roam about the streets looking for employment or resort to begging. These situations have been aggravated by lack of skills, opportunities for training and re-training and lack of committed action to promote job creation by private and community entrepreneurs (NDLEA, 2012). Frustration arising from these problems lead to recourse in Substance Abuse for temporarily removing the tension and problems arising from it. The increasing economic deterioration that leads to poverty and disempowerment of the people has driven many parents to send their children out in search of a means of earning something for contribution to family income.

The African seminar on problems of drug dependence held in Lagos Nigeria in 2011 declared that “Substance Abuse and dependence producing substances are widely prevalent in African countries have continue to increase. These problems affect the individual, the family and the society in general. Substance abuse which was originally conceived as the problem of a selected few is today becoming a problem of a sizeable proportion of the world population. The problem is so grave that it has extended beyond the usual characteristic profile of abusers being male, adult, and urban-based to now include females, youngsters and those who live in rural areas. Its economic effect is so devastating that it is estimated that the annual retail cost of psychotropic substances by prescription is over two billion naira while the alcoholic industry which produces over five billion gallons of alcoholic beverages annually generate more than four billion naira from sales to a consumer population of about 30-35 million people (Everest, 2005).

Illicit Drug traffic known to generate huge profit and fortune and that is one reason why it has been very difficult to combat the drug traffic in spite of several laws that have been promulgated. For instance, it has been estimated that the sum of \$400 billion is the turnover of illicit drug industry, which is equivalent of approximately 8% of total international trade and therefore larger than the trade in iron steel, motor vehicle, textile, tourism (NDLEA,

2017). Substance Abuse and other associated problems constitute a major threat to the survival and effective functioning of human societies, lives are lost daily through addiction and activities of addicts. A significant number of deaths from accidents and violent crimes have been traced to the activities of persons under the influence of drugs. Treatment facilities nationwide are now gradually being over burdened with drug-related problems and cases (Ndeti, 2010). The need to prevent Substance Abuse among the general population and by the growing generation of Nigeria thus becomes imperative.

Nigeria which once served only as trans-shipment route for drugs soon became a “consumer” country when it was observed that the increasing incidence of Substance Abuse among students is a contributory factor in the ugly confrontation between school administrators and students. The problem of Substance Abuse poses a far greater health hazard than most imagine. Psychoactive drugs and substances have the primary effect on the mind such as altering mood, feelings, perceptions and behaviors. These drugs are usually taken to give insulation from the real world and its difficulties. This is accompanied by the feeling that varies according to the drugs used. This is common to those whose personality development is insufficient to enable them cope with the normal life (Routledge, 2014).

Substance Abuse problems during adolescence are the single most predictive factor for adult drug dependence. Nigerian youth, a large proportion of whom is secondary school students face the greatest risk as they are targeted for recruitment into substance use by drug peddlers (Nwankwo, Obi & Nwosu, 2009). There is a dearth of data on knowledge, attitude and practice regarding alcohol and drug use, as well as how various factors influence Substance Abuse among tertiary institution students in Nigeria and particularly in Northern Nigeria. Furthermore, the few studies (Nwankwo, Obi & Nwosu, 2009) that have been undertaken in Nigeria regarding prevalence of Substance Abuse give varying sets of statistics, indicating that each area possesses its unique contextual factors that influence teenage Substance Abuse. So, this study is of utmost significance because it will provide latest and accurate statistics on the menace of Substance Abuse in the study area.

II. AIM AND OBJECTIVES

The purpose of this study was to determine the Prevalence of Substance Abuse among tertiary institution students in Nigeria. Specifically, the study will:

1. Identify the factors responsible for Substance Abuse among Substance Abusers tertiary institution students in Nigeria.
2. Ascertain the level of consumption of Substance Abuse among tertiary institution students in Nigeria.
3. Determine the consequences of Substance Abuse among Substance Abusers among tertiary institution students in Nigeria.

III. LITERATURE REVIEW

Concept of Substance Abuse

Substance Abuse is now known to be a common term referred to any use of illicit substances. Legally, the term means any use of drugs that have been classified as illegal in a country. Medically, the term means the use of any drug in a way that is harmful to the body either immediately or in the long term. It also connotes taking drugs without medical advice. Socially, the term indicates that the effects of the substance being used interfere with the

individual's social life (Folawiyo, 2018). It is also defined as the use of a drug or alcohol which is viewed as posing a problem by the society concerned (National Drug Law Enforcement Agency (NDLEA), 2011). Thus, Substance Abuse generally refers to drug use that result in the physical, mental, emotional and social impairment of the user. Abused substances include alcohol, tobacco products, stimulants, cannabis, sedative-hypnotics and narcotics. These drugs or substances of abuse belong to and heterogeneous pharmacological group and the link between them is that the sensation of euphoria they produce and the abusers want to continue to enjoy the effect.

This becomes problematic as the desire for more of the substance takes the better part of an individual and makes him live in a way that the community can no longer accept. Besides, the habit which he develops causes him or the community some harm or danger. The major problem that arises from the consumption of psychoactive drugs is dependence, the compulsion to use the drugs despite any deterioration in health, work, or social activities. Dependence varies from drug to drug in its extent and effect (Folawiyo, 2018). Substance Abuse is a problem that is caused by social, economic, political, legal and cultural factors existing within the society. Most of these factors determine the typical pattern of drugs that are being abused in Nigeria. Substance Abuse blocks meaningful use of time, energy and creative thinking and destroy a person's ambition to become great, making him hopeless and unproductive. These serious facts notwithstanding, various research reports have confirmed that Nigerian youth in both urban and rural areas and of different socio-economic backgrounds have indulged in the use and abuse of dangerous and illicit drugs. Nigerian youth face the problems of drug use as means of escaping immediate difficulties. Studies conducted (Oguntunde, 2001 and Falope, 2011) showed that youths accounts for about 70% of the population engaged in drug, again bearing in mind that the youths of this country constituted about 43% of the entire population, then Substance Abuse has an alarming negative influence on the future of the country, therefore there is much cause for alarm and concern. The problem of drugs and Substance Abuse are multi factorial, which seem to defy known and existing solutions, not only in the third world countries, but even in the technologically advanced nations. No single approach seems to effectively work; no single theory seems to adequately unravel the mysteries, and no profession can claim monopoly of the knowledge of dealing with and/or handling the problem.

The history of using mind-altering drugs to excess, or in a manner disapproved by society, is as old as the human race. Fermented beverages were probably used by prehistoric humans, who depicted their effects on cave walls. Opium and marijuana have been in worldwide use for centuries and the Indians of South America recognized the stimulant properties of the coca plant long before the Spanish conquest. It is stated that all naturally occurring sedatives, narcotics, euphoriant hallucinogens and excitants were discovered thousands of years back (Orubu, 2013).

Each society develops rules and guidelines for the use of drugs. Although the bible frequently mentions wine in approving terms, it warns against drunkenness. In some cultures, men may drink fermented beverages to intoxication, women and children who do so may be punished. Alcohol use is widely accepted in western society, but its use is prohibited and condemned in Islamic cultures. In the eastern world, opium was once a widely accepted recreational drug. In the United State and England, it was available on grocery store shelves until the late nineteenth century Cocaine, the ingredient that was responsible about 100 years ago for making Coca-Cola "the pause that refreshes" is now an illegal drug in the United States.

Drug and Substance Abuse from a Global Perspective

Drugs are said to be as old as man himself. Use and abuse of drugs had had a long history in many cultures and societies (Musk & De Klerk 2003). Natural plants like opium, coca and cannabis among others have been in use for many years. Priests in religious ceremonies have used cannabis, healers have used opium for medicinal purposes and the general population has used nicotine and caffeine in socially approved ways. In Colonial America alcohol was not only widely available as a beverage but also served as a valuable remedy for many medicinal purposes. The Incas of South America took cocaine which had a central role in their religious and social systems throughout civilization which stretched from around AD 1200 to AD 1550 (Wolmer, 1990). Immigrant Mexican laborers introduced marijuana during the 1920s to the South Western United States. During the Vietnam War, a high rate of heroin use by American military personnel occurred due to the almost pure supply of inexpensive heroin in Southeast Asia. All alcoholic beverages contain the same active ingredient ethyl alcohol or ethanol. Ethanol's % ranges from low levels around 3% to 4% in beer, 12% to 14% for wines, 45% to 50% for distilled spirits such as liquor.

The earlier man explored the properties of every plant, fruit, root and nut he would find. The use of these products therefore would be determined by their pharmacological effects due to the experiences that were new and also by a particular group's pattern of living. In one territory a substance might be used as a love potion, in another as a sacred food or drink for religious ceremonies (Kombo, 2005). By 20th century mass addiction had spread to other countries including the US. Poverty, crime and disorderly public conduct created by excessive use of alcohol led to reform movements for example the American Temperance Society in 1833. Some substance abuse may have been the effect rather than the cause of poverty and oppression. Thomas Szass, a prominent Psychiatrist and critic of many social policies restricting choice contended that drugs served as a convenient scapegoat for the social ills of urban life (Szass, 1987).

The development of medicinal Chemistry resulted in several synthetic compounds such as barbiturates, benzodiazepines and amphetamines. These were originally proposed for use as therapeutic compounds for restoration of health. Later the compounds were refined to more potent compounds and faster routes of administration were devised which favor most rapid transport of central nervous system contributing to abuse. The attitude of society and pattern of use of psychoactive substances have changed over time. The global context in the use of drugs indicates the erosion of traditional theoretical boundaries which also affect the beliefs, value systems and perceptions towards use of drugs (Gakuru, 2012). The issue of drug and substance abuse is a major headache to societies and authorities from the cities of North America, Latin America and Asia (Ngesu et al, 2008).

Psychoactive substances pose a significant threat to the health, social and economic status of families, communities and nations. The number of drug users especially alcohol is aged between 15 and 29. These die from alcohol-related cases resulting in 9% of all deaths. 15.3 persons have been associated with drug use and injecting drug use reported in 148 countries of which 120 report HIV infection among this population (WHO report, 2012). It is estimated that 10% of the adult population of the US has alcohol abuse or dependence. Morphine constitutes 10% by weight of opium, the samples used by drug abusers can vary from 2.6% to 9.9% (Kalant, 1977).

In Africa, youth and adults, rich and poor, rural and urban people abuse drugs (United Nations Drug Control Program, 1998). They add that drug abuse is more common among

men than women but the situation is changing rapidly as substance abuse among women is less visible and more private. It is noted that beer is preferred by younger males but wine is preferred by women, younger drinkers, educated people and those with low illness. Liquor is preferred by males, heavier drinkers, less educated people, middle aged and older people and those who are at a higher risk for major diseases. Over the recent years many African countries including Kenya, have had an upsurge in the production, distribution and consumption of drugs and substances with the youth mostly affected. Many of these countries have become markets for drugs as a result of the activities of organization and individual traffickers who use Africa as a transit point in their trade with the countries in the North (Affinith, 2002).

The drug problem has resulted in Africa countries developing their own drug control policies. Many have adopted anti-drug laws or legislation or established drug control agencies. Many of these countries are signatories to United Nations Drug Conventions (UNDC), United Nations Office on Drug and related Crime (UNODC) and United Nations International Drug Control Program (UNIDCP). Globally therefore, the overall drug consumption continues to spread. In Nigeria, drug and substance abuse had not been given much thought until the 1990s. This was probably because the vice was not considered a major problem among the people of Nigeria. The youth were not being given the facts about drug and substance abuse because people are always afraid of talking about such things. Recent evidence shows that a number of students and non-students abuse substances, the majority of the students being in secondary and tertiary institutions (NDLEA, 2006).

The most commonly abused drugs in Nigerian Secondary schools are tobacco, khat, alcohol, cannabis, cocaine, stimulants and tranquilizers. Alcohol abuse in Nigeria is quite alarming (Edward & Anif, 1990). The non-medical use of drugs is increasingly seen rightly or wrongly as a major social and public health problem in Nigeria when affects not only the users and abusers themselves but also their families as a whole (Mauri and Acuda, 1983). There are many bhang plantations that continue to thrive in Mt. Nigeria and Western regions. Miraa is a multibillion shifting legal drug industry (Ngunyi, 2007).

Prescription drugs are also abused nearly by those who have access to them like doctors, pharmacists and those working in medical environments. Some people do not wish to have their illness known to other persons including doctors but they have vague ideas of what type of medicine to take. In Nigeria, alcohol and diverse types of substances that are permitted or prohibited by law are readily available to adults and to a growing number of young people, both female and male students and non-students together (NDLEA, 2003). A preliminary survey was conducted among secondary school students in Nigeria and the results confirmed that drug abuse was quite prevalent among secondary school students. The study also revealed that the problem was more acute in urban schools as compared to rural schools.

Nairobi and Mombasa are notoriously known for being transit routes for illegal substances (Aden, 2006). Drug abuse is widely spread used in Nairobi. An example is in the year 2000 in which many Nigerians about 130 died at Mukurukwa Njenga and Mukuru Kayaba. Many went blind and hundreds of others were hospitalized after consuming illegal brewed poisonous liquor called kurnikumi containing methanol and other additives such as car battery acid and formalin. In Nigerian streets, many street boys and girls can be found sniffing many kinds of inhalants like cobbler's glue, petrol and other substances. This is the way these children express frustration, hopelessness and powerlessness (Otieno, 1979). Drug and substance abuse is therefore rampant in Nairobi. The assumption is therefore, that in Starches District, drug and substance abuse is rampant just like in the other parts of Nairobi.

Theoretical Frame Work

Theories of various orientations emphasize that the individual possesses a wide repertoire of behavior (Maier, 1970). Maier (1970) suggests that an individual is "a community of selves" from which the individual may adopt different perspectives further stating that this "community of selves" of individuals represents a flexible framework within which to represent many aspects of their experiences in relation to themselves and others. The theories highlighted below are employed in this study to shed light on the drug use and abuse issues surrounding the secondary school students. This study is guided by Bandura (1986) Social Cognitive Learning Theory. According to this theory behavior is determined by the persons thought processes, the environment and attitude. This means that individuals determine their own behavior while being influenced by the environmental factors and their own behavior. Bandura's social cognitive learning theory tends to focus more on cognitive expectancies, vicarious learning and self-regulations as explanatory mechanism of drugs and substance abuser. For example, individuals who believe that alcohol will make them more attractive, less inhibited, better lovers and more fun to be around, will be more prone to use alcohol. Bandura (1986) contended that behavior is largely regulated by cognitive factors such as perception of an issue and the pattern within the environment. This theory relevant to this research as it emphasizes the role of observational learning with regard to the presence and influence of models. The theory claims that role modeling does not only affects behaviors' but that it also leads to the development of thoughts and emotions that shape behavior. Students, who get engaged in the behavior of drugs and substance abuse, have most likely learnt the behavior from their environment. These students have decided to get into the behavior of drugs and substance abuse more often than not out of choice.

The Modified Social Stress Model (MSSM)

For in-depth understanding of drug use and abuse, modified social stress model guides this study. The model was developed by Rodes and Jason (1988) and modified by World Health Organization/Programme on Substance Abuse (WHO/PSA) to include the effects of drugs or substances, the personal response of the individual to drugs and additional environmental, social and cultural variables. The theory maintains that there are factors that encourage Substance Abuse called risk factors. Factors that make people less likely to abuse drugs are called protective factors. The key to health and healthy families is increasing the protective factors while decreasing the risk factors. According to this model, if many risk factors are present in a person's life, that person is more likely to begin, intensify and continue the use of drugs, which could lead to Substance Abuse. The model identifies risk factors as stress (which could be due to the school or home environment, and adolescent developmental changes) and normalization of substance use which could be seen in terms of legality and law enforcement; availability and cost of drugs; advertising, sponsorship and promotion through media, as well as the cultural value attached to various drugs. In addition, there is also the experience derived from the use of drugs, which could be positive or negative. Drugs which produce positive effects are likely to be abused. The model also showed that the more protective factors are present, the less likely the person is to become involved with drugs. Protective factors are identified as: attachments with people such as family members, peers and institutions such as religion and school. In addition are skills, which refer to physical and performance capabilities that help people succeed in life and reduce incidents of Substance Abuse. Availability of resources, within the person or the environment, which help people meet their emotional and physical needs, are said to reduce dependence on drugs. Examples include positive role models, religious faith, anti-drug campaigns plus guidance and counseling services.

According to this model, it is easy to understand the drug problem better if both risk and protective factors are considered at the same time. Probability of Substance Abuse is determined by these factors. The framework is useful as a way of planning interventions to prevent or treat problems related to Substance Abuse. Once the risk factors are identified, work can begin on reducing the risks and strengthening the protective factors. Although Rodes and Jason's theory could explain why the youth in schools do or do not abuse drugs, it is not exhaustive. In addition to the above risk and protective factors there could be others which contribute to the present scenario of Substance Abuse in families, schools and communities, as suggested in the literature review. The presence of risk and protective factors is context dependent and the proportions of their contribution depend on intensity in given situations.

Factors Responsible for Substance Abuse among the Youths

Substance Abuse is a global practice with several causes of varying origins. Any incidence of Substance Abuse can be linked to either a precipitating or maintaining factors the former factor refers to the initial and, normally, reasonable excuse for using drugs, while the latter represents reasons for maintaining the use of drugs which marks or leads to physical or psychological dependence on drugs (Folawiyo, 2018).

There is no simple cause of Substance Abuse, many factors have been indicted as the causes of Substance Abuse and reasons for Substance Abused are complex. Most drug users started using drugs as adolescents. Reports noted that youth today misuse or abused drugs because of so many reasons among which include availability of the drugs, social pressure, peer pressure, curiosity or experimentation, to rebel against constituted authority, for frustration, expression of maturity, vulnerable personality, sleep inducing, to increase work output, search for identity, religious obligations, rejection of society, ignorance of the implications of abuse, etc. (Adesina, 2005).

However, Curiosity/experimentation of drugs does motivate youths into drugs like first experience that may produce a state of arousal such as happiness and pleasure which in turn motivates them to continue, but many youngsters desire to experiment with drugs for fancy and mature decision eventually follows with regard to tobacco, alcohol and other substances which are classified as drugs. Research studies by Garba, (2008) and Abayomi, (2012) have shown that since there is a thin line between a use and misuse of drugs, individuals who lack maturity, self-esteem, confidence and accurate information are vulnerable to abuse of drugs.

In Essence, adolescent and young adults are most prone to Substance Abuse, Folawiyo, (2018). A survey carried out revealed that 2,660 secondary school students in Lagos state abused drugs as early as 11 years (for prescription drugs) and 16 years (for narcotic drugs). Among the major reasons given by the subjects for their involvement in such behavior are to feel like adults, to feel good, to get excited, to be like their friends and to be like stars. Compiled records of Mental Health Institutions in Nigeria found that Substance Abuse patients were almost within the 21 – 30 years age bracket. The findings of these researches of the Mental Health Records (MHR, 2014), therefore, revealed that there is a higher likelihood that a young person will abuse drugs than an older person.

In another development, Abayomi, (2012) identified that peer group pressure plays a crucial role in abuse of substance among the youth, he stressed further that many young person's starts to use drugs through the influence of friend. This practice is part among students, interaction with a member of peer group who engages in drug influences all the group members because of the socio-cultural process, in which experienced users essentially

“teach” new users what to anticipate, how to interpret the effects, what effects to enjoy and what effect to reinforce. The idea that a person experiences when misusing a particular drug is influenced by his or her expectation about the drug effects and by who is present in the drug-taking setting.

In a related development, the easiness with which drugs can be obtained and the relative tolerance of Substance Abuse by community, religious or political leaders have been identified by Adegbokun, (2008) as serious causes of Substance Abuse in schools and outside the schools in many countries in the world today.

In another development, environment and media also play an important role in introducing and maintaining Substance Abuse among students. Advertisements and exotic films demonstrate messages that success in both work, sport, leisure is facilitated through the chemistry of drug, and that drugs are effective instruments for success, improving mood and creating euphoria, (Abdullahi, 2000).

In the same vein, the ease and speed with which information about drugs abuse and consumption is disseminated on media across the world targeted countries, and the rapid socio-cultural changes taking place especially in the third world countries have been identified as an enabling condition for the spread of Substance Abuse (Obot, 2009).

Also increasing economic deterioration, leading to poverty, unemployment and disempowerment of the poor have contributed to the problem of Substance Abuse particularly in Nigeria. This situation has been aggravated by the lack of skills and opportunities for training and retraining, and the lack of committed actions to promote job creation by government, private and community entrepreneurs. Frustration arising from these problems leads to recourse to drug to temporarily remove the effect of frustration and problems arising from it (Abdullahi, 2000).

In addition, family personality patterns, their parenting and socio-economic status tends to influence the culture of Substance Abuse among youth. Studies by World Health Organization (2014) and National Drugs Law Enforcement Agency (2015) have showed that families that witnessed excessive punishment, brutality, incessant harassment, matrimonial divorce/conflict, lack of adequate parental care and love tend to drive youths to seek refuge in drug. The family's hold on youths has become loose these days as a result of growing poverty and continuous quest for material gains. In Nigeria today, like in most developing countries, life is a constant struggle to obtain even the basic essentials of life and many parents have no time to supervise their children's activities both at home and in school. Studies by Odejide and Peter (2009) have showed that youth from less intact families (single parent household, single parent with multiple partners, drug/alcohol dependence in a family member including rich men children) have higher rates of substance abuse. It was found that sons of alcohol parent have 25% chance of becoming alcoholic themselves (Odejide, 2009).

Consequences of Substance Abuse

From the foregoing, it is apparent that the abuse of drugs constitutes a menace to the society, and has devastating effects on the youth. It affects their future since they engage in the habit at a transitional period between childhood and adulthood. Substance Abuse produces negative effect on the user, his family and larger society. The abuser faces risks that are both psychological and physiological. These risks range from panic, irritability, depression, anxiety, psychosis, insomnia, brain damage, loss of motivation, lack of interest in constructive activities and even death (Obot, 2009).

According to Obot, (2009), the adverse consequences of Substance Abuse on human internal organs like brain, liver, pancreases, medical conditions like hypertension, chronic cough and above all some researchers have shown that HIV infection associated with drugs addiction is becoming a significant socio pathological problem in Nigeria and other countries. Obot (2009) study on substance abuse and human immuno deficiency virus disease among 641,086 cases of AIDS in the United States had been reported to the Centers of Diseases Control and Prevention, of which 31.5% were associated with illicit drug use. The sharing of needles by addicts carries the risk of direct transmission of hepatitis B and HIV. Drug use also increases a person's risk-taking behavior including unsafe sexual practices.

In addition, Substance Abuse leads to depression, anxiety, dementia, hallucination, moodiness and aggressiveness leading to the degeneration of the individual. Such individual with these characteristics is a waste to himself and the society at large.

In another development, social consequences of substance abuse to nation are quite enormous. This is because preponderance of youth roaming about the streets has negatively affected the economy as a result of low productivity and shortage of efficient manpower. As well as public safety is subverted as a result of drug addiction which lead to influx of both commercial sex workers or prostitution and series of criminality in the country. Attempt to establish a correlation between criminal violence and Substance Abuse had been made and there are claims that illicit drug users are higher in the population of criminals than non-drug user.

However, violence witnessed in various communities leading to bloodletting, arson, rape, stealing has a link with Substance Abuse. The human and material resources lost during such violence have their tolls on the stability of the nation. A significant number of deaths from road accidents have also been traced to the act of persons under the influence of drugs. Other negative effects of Substance Abuse on the family and the society at large can be attributed to the sudden increase in aggression, violence destruction, gangsters, defiance of constituted authority, maladjustment, riots, demonstration etc. among adolescent and young adult, it therefore becomes imperative to put machineries in place to control the menace of Substance Abuse.

Many youth that abuse drugs appear to have personality disorder before taking drugs as shown by poor school record, truancy, delinquency and dropout. Such Substance Abusers often seem to be without resources to cope with the challenges of day-to-day life; they are inconsistent in their feelings and critical of society and authority. Some Substance Abusers give a history of mental illness or personality disorder in the family. Studies found a higher risk for those children with a mental disorder to progress from experimentation into problematic usage of substance than those in a community. Hospital records from different psychiatric hospitals in Nigeria revealed that Substance Abusers were mostly youth (58%) within the 21 – 30-year age bracket, majority of them (91%) were males and were single (58%) and 17% were students (Adegbokun, 2008).

Level of Consumption of Substance Abuse among the Youth

About 230 million people, or 5 percent of the world's adult population, are estimated to have abused drug at least once in 2010 (WDR, 2012). Alcohol and other drugs (Khat and tobacco) users' number about 27 million, which is 0.6 percent of the world adult population (UNODC, 2014). What is more surprising is that, alcohol alone kill around 0.2 million people each year, shattering families and bringing misery to thousands of other people (Sampou, 2013). Similarly, WDR (2012) reported that, alcohol and drug use undermine economic and social

development and contributes to crime, instability, insecurity and the spread of HIV. Not only that, alcohol and drug abuse is major burdens to society; causing economic costs, health cost, crime-related costs and losses in productivity (Deressa & Azazh, 2011).

Recent trends indicate that the use of substances, mainly alcohol, chewing khat and smoking cigarette have dramatically increased particularly in developing countries (Watson, 2012). Alcohol, especially in high doses, or when combined with khat or tobacco, continues to claim the lives of many people. It is estimated that 9% of the global population aged 12 or older are classified with dependence on psychoactive substances such as alcohol (Martens, O'Connor & Beck, 2006). Heavy consumption of alcohol when shared with chewing Khat is associated with many psychological problems including euphoria, hyperactivity, anorexia, insomnia, lethargy and depression. In addition, the combined use of alcohol and khat increase sexual risky behavior contributing to the spread of HIV infection (Watson, 2012). Over 815,000 students were abusing substances out of which 367,050 were girls (Nweke, 2013).

A baseline survey on drug and substance abuse in the years 2009 and 2010 revealed that more than a fifth of primary school pupils in Nigeria have taken alcohol and the figure rises to more than three-fourths for university students (WHO, 2011). Sampou (2013) found out that in Nigeria, more than 22.7% of the primary school children have taken alcohol, a figure that rises to 57.9% in secondary schools and to 68% among university students. A large number of students across all age groups have been exposed to alcohol, tobacco, "Igbo", (Marijuana), glue, and even hard substances such as heroin and cocaine. During the annual general meeting of Secondary Schools Principals in Imo State, Nigeria in 2009, a shocking statistic was revealed on the prevalence of substance abuse in secondary schools in the country. It was documented that 33.3% take alcohol, 8.3% smoke cigarettes, 3.0% to 9.1% smoke marijuana/Igbo (Anyahie, 2009). Ibekwe (2011) and Ogu (2011) agree on the following behaviors exhibited by those who abuse substances; watering eyes and nose, unusually talkative hence noise making, unusual quietness, unpredictable temper, concentration lapse, and loss of interest in education.

The problem of substance abuse is so grave that though it was originally conceived as the problem of a 'select few', it has extended beyond the usual characteristics of abusers being male, adult and urban based people to now include female, youngsters and rural dwellers. These abusers erroneously believe that drugs enhance their performance, put them in good mood (Ajala, 2009). In Nigeria, alcohol and cigarette are legal substances but, the two have been discovered to cause physical damage to human bodies. These substances have also said to be "gateway drugs" to other more potent drugs like heroin and cocaine (UNDCP, 2008). In Nigeria, it has been reported that smoking (tobacco) causes 90.0% of lung cancer, 30.0% of all cancers, and 80.0% of other chronic lung diseases (Shokunbi, 2010).

This behavior has been found to lead to the trying out of new experiences such as drugs, sex, sometimes with dire consequence for the adolescent. This behavior warrants urgent scrutiny in Nigeria as studies carried out over the last two decades have identified adolescents as a major group involved in the misuse of psychoactive substances. In many urban areas, psychoactive substances can be easily obtained from kiosks, bars, restaurants, and street vendors. With an increase in demand and ever-growing population of users, human trafficking and associated crimes are rising. In many countries, psychoactive substance use appears closely linked to an increase in availability and access to the substances by a large proportion of the community (Deressa & Azazh, 2011). Intoxication, accidental or violent injury, self-harm, sexually transmitted diseases, teenage pregnancy, abortion and psychiatric

disorder are on the increase in our world today⁵. Substance abuse has both psychological, health, and social effects to the individual.

In 2002, the world health organization estimated that 140 million people were alcohol-dependent and another 400 million suffered alcohol related problems (Deressa & Azazh, 2011). In 2008, the mortality due to tobacco smoking was estimated to be more than 5million deaths annually⁷ and by 2020; it is projected to be 10 million⁸. A study among students in Poland showed that 99.5% of students used alcohol. There was statistically higher frequency of beer consumption in males than in females. The overall rate of smoking was found to be 29.6% among adolescent students in Kolkata, India while 37% of males and 13.5% of females were found to be current smokers.

In a study done in Enugu, Nigeria, among secondary school adolescents, prevalence rate of substance abuse was 71.7%. About 82% (81.5%) of the adolescent substance users were males against 18.4% that were females, giving a male-female ratio of approximately.

Summary of Reviewed Related Literature

Literatures cited has shown that Substance Abuse is a problem that is caused by social, economic, political, legal and cultural factors existing within the society. Most of these factors determine the typical pattern of drugs that are being abused in Nigeria. Substance Abuse blocks meaningful use of time, energy and creative thinking and destroy a person's ambition to become great, making him hopeless and unproductive. These serious facts notwithstanding, various research reports have confirmed that Nigerian youth in both urban and rural areas and of different socio-economic backgrounds have indulged in the use and abuse of dangerous and illicit drugs. Nigerian youth face the problems of drug use as means of escaping immediate difficulties.

Many literatures have proven that there is no simple cause of Substance Abuse, many factors have been indicted as the causes of Substance Abuse and reasons for Substance Abused are complex. Most drug users started using drugs as adolescents. Reports noted that youth today misuse or abused drugs because of so many reasons among which include availability of the drugs, social pressure, peer pressure, curiosity or experimentation, to rebel against constituted authority, for frustration, expression of maturity, vulnerable personality, sleep inducing, to increase work output, search for identity, religious obligations, rejection of society, ignorance of the implications of abuse, etc

Since the problem of Substance Abuse in schools is largely a problem among the student population, the support of the students themselves has to be enlisted in controlling, preventing or eliminating the problem among them. The more students are involved in anti-Substance Abuses efforts; the more they would be able to use their creative potential toward solving the problem. Thus, the school authorities and others members of the school community can use the registered, societies, clubs, associations, unions, organizations and other students' groups to propagate anti-Substance Abuse messages.

Many studies cited above have been carried out on the causes and impact of Substance Abuse in various part of Nigeria, but very few have been done in the area of the study among post primary school students in Kaduna Metropolis. Therefore, this study will try to fill this gap by investigating the Prevalence of Substance Abuse among post primary school students in Kaduna Metropolis.

IV. METHODOLOGY

The descriptive survey design was used for this study because it has the advantage of producing good responses from wide subject (Borg and Gall 1989). Descriptive survey design dwelled on the need to conduct a study on an entire population of respondents or items by collecting relevant data from samples considered as true representation of the whole population.

The researcher is interested in describing the Prevalence of Substance Abuse among post primary school students in Kaduna Metropolis.

Area of the Study

Nigerian Army College of Environmental Science and Technology Makurdi is located in Nigerian Army School of Military Engineering (NASME) in North bank Makurdi, Benue state. Benue state is in middle belt region of Nigeria. It is primarily inhabited by the major tribes, Tivs and Idoma including other tribes, and it is predominantly an agricultural region. Benue State is located within longitude 8° 44' 59.99" E and latitude 7° 19' 60.00" N with a land mass of 534,059km² with over 20 tertiary institutions across the state

Population/Sample and Sampling Technique

The target populations of this study involve all the students in Nigerian Army College of Environmental Science and Technology Makurdi. Researcher used simple random sampling. A total of 357 students out of 1530 students was sampled. This sample is considered adequate based on the recommendation of Krejcie and Morgan (1970) sample determination table. This is also in line with the realization of Owolabi, (2005) who stated that the sample size should be adequate in order to ensure an acceptable representation of the population. Structured questionnaire was used to collect data which was validated and tested for consistency.

Data Analysis

The data collected were analyzed using the mean statistical tool and standard deviation in which results were presented in tables and discussed where recommendations were made.

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The following table presents the results of the data collected for this research work in Nigerian Army College of Environmental Science and Technology Makurdi. The data presented reflects the finding and recommendations in curbing the menace of drug abuse in tertiary institution in Nigeria.

Section A: Demographic Information

The data collected in this category was intended to find out the distribution of the respondents based on Gender, Age and Educational Qualification of respondents. The Frequency (f) for each category was found and percentages (%) calculated as shown in the tables and charts below.

Table 1: Gender of the Respondents

Gender of the Respondents	Frequency	Percentage %
Male	140	41
Female	201	59
Total	341	100

Source: Field Survey, 2025

The above table 1 indicates that 140 respondents representing (41%) are male while the remaining 201 respondents representing (59%) are females.

Table 2: Age Distribution of Respondents

Age	Frequency	Percentage %
18-20yrs	62	18
21-25	69	20
26-30	121	35
31-35	53	16
36 and above	36	11
Total	341	100

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Table 2 indicates that 62 respondents representing (18%) are between 18 – 20 years, 69 respondents representing (20%) are between 21 – 25 years, 121 respondents representing (35%) are between 26 – 30 years, 53 respondents representing (16%) are between 31 – 35 years while the remaining 36 respondents representing (11%) are between 36 years and above.

Table 3: Educational Qualification of Respondents

Educational Qualification	Frequency	Percentage %
SSCE/GCE	197	57.7
NCE/OND	84	24.6
HND/BSC/B. A	41	12
Others	19	5.7
Total	341	100

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Table 3 indicates that, 197 respondents representing (57.7%) are having SSCE/GCE, 84 respondents representing (24.6%) are having NCE/OND, 41 respondents representing (12%) are having HND/BSC/BA while the remaining 19 respondents representing (5.7%) are having other forms of educational qualification.

Section B: Results of Research Questions

Research Question One: What are the factors responsible for Substance Abuse among tertiary institution students in Nigeria?

Table 4: Mean responses on the Factors Responsible for Substance Abuse

S/No	Items	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	Remarks
1	Availability of the drugs	145	142	25	29	3.18	Accepted
2	Social pressure	91	200	20	30	3.03	Accepted
3	Peer pressure	200	123	5	13	3.50	Accepted
4	Curiosity or experimentation	96	165	26	54	2.89	Accepted
5	Rebellion against constituted authority	78	118	45	100	2.51	Accepted
6	Frustration	101	192	20	28	3.07	Accepted
7	Sleep inducing	121	177	23	20	3.17	Accepted
8	Increased work output	73	48	218	2	2.56	Accepted
9	Rejection	51	90	83	117	2.22	Rejected
10	Ignorance of the implications of abuse	101	192	20	28	3.07	Accepted

Grand Mean = 2.92

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Table 4 above indicated that respondents agreed with items 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11 and 13 and disagreed with item 12 with a grand mean of 2.92.

Research Question Two: What is the level of consumption of Substance Abuse among Substance Abusers among Post Primary School Students in Kaduna Metropolis?

This research question was answered in Table 5 below:

Table 5: Responses on Level of Consumption of Substance Abuse among tertiary institution students in Nigeria

S/no	Items	ED	EW	ETW	EM	Mean	Remarks
14	Alcoholic/beer	101	192	20	28	3.07	Accepted
15	Cigarette	91	200	20	30	3.03	Accepted
16	India hemp	13	5	200	123	1.73	Rejected
17	Tramadol	26	54	96	165	1.83	Rejected
18	Cough syrup	45	100	78	118	2.21	Rejected
19	Diazepam	-	-	-	-	0	Rejected
20	Opiodanalgestics	121	177	23	20	3.17	Accepted
21	Whisky hot	73	48	218	2	2.56	Accepted
22	Petrol	83	117	51	90	2.57	Accepted
23	Pit latrine	25	29	145	142	1.82	Rejected
24	Codeine	101	192	20	28	3.07	Accepted

Grand Mean= 2.79

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Table 5 above indicated that respondents agreed with items 14, 15, 20, 21, 22, 24, while disagreed with items 16, 17, 18, 19 and 23 a grand mean of 2.79. These showed that the level of consumption of substance abuse among substance abusers among post primary school students in kaduna metropolis is high.

Research Question Three: What are the Consequences of Substance Abuse among Substance Abusers among tertiary institution students in Nigeria?

Table 6: Mean responses on the consequences of Substance Abuse

S/No	Items	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	Remarks
25	Panic	134	157	30	20	3.19	Accepted
26	Irritability	75	188	23	55	2.83	Accepted
27	Depression	54	200	40	47	2.76	Accepted
28	Anxiety	290	21	15	15	3.72	Accepted
29	Psychosis	125	170	15	31	3.14	Accepted
30	Insomnia	201	109	8	23	3.43	Accepted
31	Brain damage	50	158	90	43	2.63	Accepted
32	Loss of motivation	134	156	24	10	3.11	Accepted
33	Lack of interest in constructive activities	290	20	20	11	3.79	Accepted
34	Pulmonary tuberculosis	79	111	51	100	2.64	Accepted

Grand Mean= 3.12

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Table 6 above indicated that respondents agreed with items 25, 26, 27, 28, 29, 30, 31, 32, 33 and 34 a grand mean of 3.12 which suggest general acceptance of all the items in the questionnaire. Individual analysis of the responses indicated that the respondents accepted all the items presented in the table with items 14 and 19 on anxiety and lack of interest in constructive activities respectively have the highest means score of 3.72 and 3.79 while item 17 on Brain damage has the lowest mean score of 2.63. These showed that the above listed items are the consequences of Substance Abuse among tertiary institution students in Nigeria.

Findings of the Study

Based on the research analysis of data shown in chapter four, the following findings were made:

1. Factors responsible for Substance Abuse among tertiary institution students in Nigeria are availability of the drugs, social pressure, Peer pressure, Curiosity or experimentation, Rebellion against constituted authority, Frustration, Sleep inducing, Increased work output and Ignorance of the implications of abuse.
2. The level of consumption of substance abuse is high in alcoholic beer, Cigarette, Codeine, Diazepam, Opioid analgesics, Whisky/hot and Petrol
3. The consequences of Substance Abuse among tertiary institution students in Nigeria include Panic, Irritability, Depression, Anxiety, Psychosis, Insomnia, Loss of motivation, Lack of interest in constructive activities and Brain damage.

VI. DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

Factors Responsible for Substance Abuse

Form research question one, it was found that availability of the drugs, social pressure, Peer pressure, Curiosity or experimentation, Rebellion against constituted authority among others are the factors responsible for Substance Abuse among tertiary institution students in Nigeria. This is conformity with the findings of Adesina, (2005) who found that Substance Abuse is a global practice with several causes of varying origins. Any incidence of Substance Abuse can be linked to either a precipitating or maintaining factors. The former factor refers to the initial and, normally, reasonable excuse for using drugs, while the latter represents reasons for maintaining the use of drugs which marks or leads to physical or psychological dependence on drugs. There is no simple cause of Substance Abuse, many factors have been indicted as the causes of Substance Abuse and reasons for Substance Abused are complex. Most drug users started using drugs as adolescents. Reports noted that youth today misuse or abused drugs because of so many reasons among which include availability of the drugs, social pressure, peer pressure, curiosity or experimentation, to rebel against constituted authority, for frustration, expression of maturity, vulnerable personality, sleep inducing, to increase work output, search for identity, religious obligations, rejection of society, ignorance of the implications of abuse, etc.

Level of Consumption of Substance Abuse

It was discovered from research question two that level of consumption of Substance Abuse among Substance Abusers among tertiary institution students in Nigeria is high. This is in agreement with study by Anyaehie, (2009) that, 33.3% take alcohol, 8.3% smoke cigarettes, 3.0% to 9.1% smoke marijuana. A study among students in Poland is also in line with this study that 99.5% of students used alcohol. There was statistically higher frequency of beer consumption in males than in females⁹. The overall rate of smoking was found to be 29.6% among adolescent students in Kolkata, India while 37% of males and 13.5% of females were found to be current smokers. In a study done in Enugu, Nigeria, among secondary school adolescents, prevalence rate of substance abuse was high⁷1.7%. About 82% (81.5%) of the adolescent substance users were males against 18.4% that were females, giving a male-female ratio of approximately.

Consequences of Substance Abuse

From research question three, it was found that Panic, Irritability, Depression, Anxiety, Psychosis among others are the consequences of Substance Abuse among post primary school students in Kaduna Metropolis. This agrees with the opinion of Obot, (2009) who said that it is apparent that the abuse of drugs constitutes a menace to the society, and has devastating effects on the youth. It affects their future since they engage in the habit at a transitional period between childhood and adulthood. Substance Abuse produces negative effect on the user, his family and larger society. The abuser faces risks that are both psychological and physiological. These risks range from panic, irritability, depression, anxiety, psychosis, insomnia, brain damage, loss of motivation, lack of interest in constructive activities and even death.

VII CONCLUSION

Access to all kinds of drugs, on the achieves in Nigeria, has led to upsurge of social vices in the society which include banditry, kidnapping, cattle roasting, sexual harassment, among

other things which has led to rebellion against constituted authority from the forgoing fact, there is need for constituted authority to take drastic measure to save the society out of pandemic and issue of insecurity.

However, prevention of the illicit demand for drugs, Treatment and rehabilitation of drug dependent persons, Control of illicit supply, Forfeiture and transfer of the instrument and proceeds of illicit drug trafficking, Prevention of illicit drug trafficking into and through Nigeria are the ways of solving the problems of Substance Abuse among tertiary institution students in Nigeria.

VIII. RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made.

1. Strict enforcement of the legal provisions that restrict exposure of young people to social places where alcohol and illicit drug are found.
2. Peer guidance among parents, stakeholders concerning the amount of money their children access and the dangers associated with that should be pursued.
3. School managements and parents need to establish a mechanism to control the amount of pocket money that their students possess.
4. Legislation regarding control of the media, especially the rogue internet is needed. Restricted advertisement of addictive substances should continue regulatory agencies like the NDLEA.

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